

TRAINING ON A CREATIVE AND MODERN APPROACH IN THE SYSTEM OF TRAINING: SOCIAL AWARENESS, INCLUSIVE ORGANIZATION EFFECTIVENESS

Djurayeva Perdegul Saidovna

National training of teachers of Navai region in new methods center, "Preschool, primary and special educational methods" department associate docent d/b

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Abstract. *Establishing a friendly relationship with children through the culture of reading, social-emotional training, social awareness, inclusion strategies in the professional development system.*

Keywords: *reading culture, social-emotional education, children's literature, discussion, reflection, awareness, inclusiveness.*

Introduction

Education based on the goals of sustainable development - based on international and national normative legal documents, establishing and adopting activities of inclusive education and primary correctional classes in schools for children with special educational needs, includes control and management procedures and the organization of the educational process, its stages, emerging problems and solutions.

Decree № PF-134 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 "On approval of the national program for the development of school education in 2022-2026", Decree № PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", According to the results of the diagnostic test conducted on the basis of the order of the Ministry of Pre-school and School Education № 540 dated November 14, 2023, a valuable attitude to inclusive education, Development of 21st century skills: 4K - new knowledge, skills, competences and relevant new knowledge, skills, skills and competences of the course participants on the educational module of critical and creative thinking, cooperation, formation of communication skills and organization of educational activities aimed at formation. Based on the content of the priorities set for the introduction of modern principles of personnel policy formation in the general secondary education system through the implementation of advanced and transparent organizational and legal mechanisms of teacher training, modern education based on modern requirements trends and their impact on the quality of education, analysis of best practices for ensuring the effectiveness of education, improvement of the content of continuous professional development processes, and regular improvement of their professional competence.

Research materials and methodology

Our main goal is to organize a session on social-emotional education in order to define the perspectives and directions of introducing result-oriented education using children's literature to develop social awareness, empathy and inclusion in students. Grade Level: Beginner (can be adapted for different learning levels). Didactic materials: age-appropriate children's literature books on social awareness and inclusiveness. Blackboard or white paper; markers. Worksheets for reflection (pre-prepared). Before starting the session, explain the importance of social awareness

and inclusivity in creating a supportive classroom community and community. Discuss the concept of inclusivity and how it involves understanding and valuing the views and experiences of others.

Search results.

Book Selection and Reading - Choose a children's book about social awareness and inclusion and read it aloud to the class. Stop at appropriate points as you read the story and encourage readers to think about the characters' experiences and feelings.

Before reading. Introduce the book, its author and illustrator. Show the title and read it. Ask students what information they learned from the book cover. Include some interesting information about the author, especially if they've read another book by that author before. Set a reading goal by relating the text to the student's existing knowledge. That is, find out what kind of knowledge children have on this topic through question and answer. Ask students to guess what the text is about. Explain why you are reading the book and what reading comprehension skills students will practice. *Recommendation:* Choose an interesting and age-appropriate text in advance. Create a comfortable reading environment. Read with enthusiasm. Encourage students to actively participate by engaging them in the learning process. Use visual aids and supporting tasks.

During the study. Read aloud, fluently and expressively. Stop and ask questions at appropriate points to discuss the text. Ask students to answer. Encourage any guesses by asking them to comment and guess. Use the turn and talk strategy. Use the turn and talk strategy. Ask students to turn to each other and ask questions about the story. Ask open-ended questions (high-level thinking questions). To answer open-ended questions, students avoid short answers such as "Yes" and "No" and use fully meaningful sentences. "Why?", "How?" Questions starting with interrogative words such as. Model and reinforce reading comprehension strategies (think aloud). Ask students what new words mean, then explain the meaning of the words using definitions and examples that children can understand.

After reading: Ask questions about the story and have a discussion. At the same time, ask students for their reactions to the content of the story. You can also ask them to give feedback on the narration, characters, events or information in the text. Discuss the parts you like. Organize additional activities for children to learn stories as they know: interpret the general content of the story or a part of it by drawing; drama/role play; writing a new ending to the story; arts and crafts to illustrate the story. For example, in the "Five Fingers" method, situation 1: analysis of an artistic text; Case 2: we will consider it in the analysis of the information text.

Introduction:

Sorting the listeners into groups according to their experience and skills. The main part: Stage 1 - "Five fingers" method: Analysis of the literary text - Characters - Time and place - Problem - Incident - Solution; For example, 4th grade "Mother language and reading literacy" in part 1 of the new generation textbook on pages 15-16 in my practical training with the audience based on the story "The Garden of Kindness", divided into 4 groups, 5 stages I conducted an analytical training with this method, and the fact that the scientific classification opinions specific to the skills of the 4K model were tried to reveal their essence within the scope of the topic formed an interest in the method.

The characters of the story, their uniqueness, what time and place it takes place, who or what is the main problem, the behavior of the teacher, mother, grandfather, Dilshad and his

classmates, a loving look, friendly environment, family, school cooperation, the idea of caring for the bereaved or the elderly, the orchard in the school yard and Dilshod's house, the smallest episode such as the coherence of events, the analysis of the creative approach, the diversity of critical thoughts, I paid attention to the fact that the existence of different views on events can be fully classified on the basis of this small story. Of course, such a creative approach was warmly received by the listeners and observers of the lesson, and it was recognized that it was effectively organized. During the story, the final conclusions, the ideas presented as a solution were accepted. Step 2: "Five Fingers" Method: Information Text Analysis - Topic - Main Idea - Information 1 - Information 2 - Information 3 - Solution.

Talents can be discovered even among children with special needs.

It is difficult for children with disabilities to learn. But if they are given enough attention, it is possible to discover talented ones even among children with special needs. Muhammad Khan, a student of the inclusive class of comprehensive school No. 215 in our capital, was born with Down syndrome. His parents paid all their attention to the development of the "sunny child". Muhammad Khan has his own dreams and plans like healthy children.

He loves sports. He also sings in his spare time. Muhammad Khan took part in the "Turkish World" sports and culture festival for special athletes, organized for the first time by the Sports Federation of Special Athletes of Turkey. He visited from Turkey, Azerbaijan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Hungary and Kyrgyzstan and was among the athletes who won in tennis and athletics. Children with disabilities like Muhammad are the majority in society. Most parents do not want them to be educated in general schools in order not to be discriminated and insulted by their peers, or do not believe that a child with special needs should receive the same attention as healthy children. According to experts, education is a life tool for people with disabilities. Because they have little opportunity to do physical work. Therefore, ensuring the education of such children helps them find a decent place in society and earn income for their needs.

Stage 3: Fantasy Beauty" strategy. Work on distributed materials. Creating individual words and sentences for each listener, expressing, creating a text as a team, giving a title to the text; For example,

family

parents

institution

attention

relationship

a child

guilty

benefit

a person

guest

value

please

ability

love

reference

training

Step 4: Provide final feedback based on the 4K model. Summary: based on Bloom's taxonomy: reasoning at the levels of knowing, understanding, applying, analyzing, summarizing, evaluating the development of thinking; The members of the group express their observations individually; Group work refers to collective observation; 4 groups should conduct a general observation based on one title; The importance of the 4K model in teaching subjects (in the case of inclusive education). Evaluation criteria: Assessment method, Case-study method, Homework in "Essay method". Aim to write an essay on the topic and present your thoughts ready for the next school year.

Discussions.

The Fryer model (Frayer diagram) is a graphic organizer. It was first invented by Dorothy Fryer and her colleagues at the University of Wisconsin (Wayne Fredrick and Herbert Clausmeyer) in 1969. The goal of Fryer's model (Frayer, 1969; Buehl, 2001) is to identify unfamiliar concepts and vocabulary. Fryer's model is a four-square model for identifying, clarifying, and analyzing the meaning and structure of words. The selected attention word is written in the middle of the sheet or paper in the form of an oval. Sometimes the part of the sentence enters the oval.

Conclusion.

Discussion with the whole class on the formation of 4K skills in the development of 21st century skills and the organization of educational activities with the students of the course on the formation of relevant new knowledge, skills, skills and competencies according to the educational module - illustrated lead a discussion about the topics of social awareness and inclusion, use a whiteboard or white paper to create a visual representation of the main ideas, concepts discussed. Encourage students to share their thoughts, reactions, and connections to the story.

In a small group activity - divide the students into small groups and give each group different children's books that promote social awareness and inclusion. Tell the groups to read their assigned book together and discuss the themes, characters and ideas of inclusion.

Ask students to find specific examples of how the characters in the story show compassion, empathy, and respect for others. Gallery Walk Strategy and Reflection - Direct each group to create a poster or exhibit with a book cover, a brief summary, and illustrations related to the themes of

social awareness and inclusion. Have a "Gallery Walk" where groups can rotate and look at each other's exhibits.

Name _____ **The date** _____

Name: _____ **Directions:** _____

<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>Fr. Inclusive - I include, Lot. Include - I include, I add. Ing. Inclusive, inclusion - to harmonize, harmonize, encompass.</p>	<p>CHARACTERISTICS</p> <p>Inclusive education is when children with special educational needs are included in the classroom with regular children.</p>
<div style="border: 1px solid green; border-radius: 50%; width: 100px; height: 100px; margin: 0 auto; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <div style="background-color: #e0e0e0; padding: 5px; text-align: center;"> PRINCIPLES OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION </div> </div>	
<p>this is the process of education and upbringing of all children, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual and other characteristics, included in the general education system. They attend mainstream schools in the community with their non-disabled peers, taking into account their special educational needs.</p> <p>EXAMPLES</p>	<p>*Opportunities are not equal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barrier-free environment • Misdiagnosis • There is no systematicity • The presence of a resource teacher is not taken into account • Community awareness is not necessary, only if it is involved in education <p>Incorrect example/synonym-antonym/illustrations</p>

Give your opinion

Individual Reflection - Distribute the reflection worksheets to each student. Ask students to reflect on the themes of social awareness and inclusivity discussed in the books and their own experiences with inclusion. Ask them how they can contribute to creating a more inclusive and empathetic environment in the classroom and in the community.

Share and Wrap Up - Allow a few students to share their ideas with the class. Summarize the main points discussed during the session, emphasizing the importance of social awareness, empathy and inclusion. Encourage students to apply their understanding of social awareness and inclusivity in their interactions and actions, and develop a more inclusive and empathetic environment. In summary, a key part of inclusive education is creating a learning-friendly environment for children to learn.

REFERENCES

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